

Innovative and Sustainable Groundwater Management in the Mediterranean

M2.4. Key Recommendation for Reinforcement of Science-Based Management in The MED Region

VERSION 0.2

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Executive Summary

The overall objective of the InTheMED project is to implement innovative and sustainable management tools and remediation strategies for the Mediterranean (MED) aquifers (inland and coastal) in order to mitigate anthropogenic and climate-change threats by creating new long-lasting spaces of social learning among different interdependent stakeholders, NGOs, and scientific researchers in five field case studies. These are located at the two shores of the MED basin, namely in Spain, Greece, Portugal, Tunisia, and Turkey.

InTheMED will develop an inclusive process that will establish an ensemble of innovative assessment and management tools and methodologies including a high-resolution monitoring approach, smart modelling, a socio-economic assessment, web-based decision support systems (DSS) and new configurations for governance to validate efficient and sustainable integrated groundwater management in the MED considering both the quantitative and qualitative aspects.

The document reports the Milestone M2.4, which summarizes the current monitoring strategies and networks of case studies countries (Spain, Greece, Portugal, Tunisia and Turkey) and gives insightful recommendations for implementing science-driven management based on in-situ data. Data needed for detailed groundwater assessment and management are listed. Then, a brief description of the groundwater monitoring systems by function and their assessment levels are presented. Also, the current groundwater monitoring networks of the five case study countries are reviewed. Finally, recommendations towards systematic monitoring and data sharing in the case studies and beyond for the whole MED region are listed.

1. Data Needed for Groundwater Management

Changing groundwater quality and quantity is often a long and slow process occurring below an extensive and not easily accessible water body that is often considered a hidden resource. Changes in these areas cannot be detected by simple one-time surveys and require more elaborate monitoring networks. Management of aquifers is fundamentally about controlling groundwater abstraction, contaminant loads and aquifer response as key inputs.

In order to evaluate the groundwater issues, it is required to collect both ‘baseline’ and ‘time-variant’ data, and the collection of time-variant data are so-called groundwater monitoring. In Table 1, some of the different types of data needed for groundwater management are reported, and each type of baseline data and time-variant data are reported. One of the most important parts of groundwater data monitoring and investigations are wells and data collected by them because they are the only way to have physical access to the aquifers. When water wells are drilled, they provide one-off unique in-situ data on the groundwater resource and its variation with depth and data acquired during drilling (borehole logging) and initial test pumping form key baseline reference information on groundwater quantity and quality, in addition to their value for the determination of abstraction well potential. A set of obstruction and observation wells are called a monitoring network.

Table 1. Types of data required for detailed groundwater assessment

Type of Data	Baseline Data (From Archives)	Time-Variant Data (From Field Stations)
Groundwater Occurrence and Aquifer Properties	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water well records (hydrogeological logs, Instantaneous groundwater levels and quality), Well and aquifer pumping tests. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Groundwater level monitoring, Groundwater quality monitoring.
Groundwater Use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water well pump installations, Water-use inventories, Population registers and forecasts, Energy consumption for irrigation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water well abstraction, Monitoring (direct or indirect), Well groundwater level variations.
Supporting Information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Climatic data, Land-use inventories, Geological maps/sections. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> River flow gauging, Meteorological observations, Satellite land-use surveys.

1.1. Cost-Effective Groundwater Monitoring

In Table 2, different monitoring network systems and their functions and well locations are reported. Groundwater monitoring is often considered expensive compared to surface water monitoring. The main components of expenditure include the:

- capital cost (of network installation),
- sampling costs (for instrumentation, personnel, and logistics) and
- analytical costs (for laboratory, data processing and storage).

Moreover, the return on initial investment is not likely to be evident immediately. So, to have an effective monitoring system:

- it is crucial to have a specific objective and
- collected data should be stored systematically for future use because historical data plays an important role in the calibration of numerical aquifer models and form the basis of a reliable simulation for future scenarios.

In this context, groundwater abstraction and use of data monitoring play an essential role, and to reduce financial and operational costs, it is reasonable to think about different data collection sources. For example, direct monitoring of groundwater abstraction in individual abstraction wells using metering tools, which is still financially not possible in all countries. In addition, it is not possible without the cooperation of water users. But it is also possible to collect data through indirect monitoring by the collection of indicative data like the estimation of the extracted water using pumping time and energy consumption of the pump, or it is possible to use remote sensing tools such as satellites and airborne sensors to collect data in a relatively large scale with a lower cost per km².

Table 2. Classification of groundwater monitoring systems by function

System	Basic Function	Well Locations
Primary (Reference Monitoring)	Evaluation of general groundwater behaviour: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trends resulting from land-use change and climatic variation, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In uniform areas with respect to hydrogeology and land use.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Processes such as recharge, flow and diffuse contamination. 	
	Protection against potential impacts of following:	
Secondary (Protection Monitoring)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strategic groundwater resource, Wellfields/springheads for public water supply, Urban infrastructure from land subsidence, Archaeological sites against rising water table, Groundwater-dependent ecosystems. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Around areas/facilities/features requiring protection.
	Early warning of groundwater impacts from:	
Tertiary (Pollution Containment)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Intensive agricultural land use, Industrial sites, Solid waste landfills, Land reclamation areas, Quarries and mines. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Immediately down-and up-hydraulic gradient from hazard.

The conventional use of remote sensing in groundwater is by geology mapping of land use, crop types, soil salinization and land subsidence, which recently have been interpreted as thermal energy sensor data to estimate actual evaporation rates, which is possible if only sufficient frequency of data is available, and the land surface is not so abrupt then both daily and dry session actual evaporation at farm and aquifer level can be estimated. As a direct measurement of changes in groundwater level, the NASA's GRACE mission provides the first product to evaluate groundwater variation from space. By monitoring changes in the Earth's gravity field, dedicated algorithms can disentangle groundwater changes from the rest of hydrological cycle variations.

These techniques are subjected to increasing error levels in low vapor fluxes. Also, their original coarser scale features reduce its accuracy at local scale and therefore cannot be used to determine actual cumulative evaporation, soil moisture deficit or aquifer recharge rates for a natural arid zone vegetation cover but it has the potential to broaden the coverage and reduce the costs.

Effectiveness of groundwater data can be increased by careful attention to:

- network design,
- system implementation,
- data interpretation,

- making the best use of data collected by past monitoring activities,
- selecting monitoring stations that, as far as possible, are easily accessible,
- making the fullest use of indicator determinants to reduce analytical cost,
- promoting complementary self-monitoring amongst water users,
- incorporating quality control and quality assurance procedures.

Sample modifications are a major source of error which can be controlled by appropriate sampling procedures. The groundwater level is the dominant and most monitored indicator for groundwater quantity assessment. While for groundwater quality, a large range of indicators and parameters can be considered depending on the characteristics of the monitored groundwater system and the monitoring strategy's objectives. In Table 3, different sampling procedures for groundwater quality assessment are reported (based on Tuinhof et al. 2005).

Table 3. Summary of sampling procedures and precautions for specific groups of groundwater taken from Tuinhof et al. 2005

Determinant Group	Sampling Procedure	Preferred Materials	Storage Time/ Temperature	Operational Difficulty /Cost
Major Ions Cl, SO ₄ , F, Na, K	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0.45 µm filter only • No acidification 	Any	7 days/4 °C	Minimal
Trace Metals Fe, Mn, As, Cu, Zn, Pb, Cr, Cd, etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sealed 0.45 µm filter • Acidify (pH <2) • Avoid aeration through splashing/head space 	Plastic	150 days	Moderate
N Species NO ₃ , NH ₄ (NO ₂)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sealed 0.45 µm filter 	Any	1 day/4 °C	Moderate/Low
Microbiological TC, FC, FS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sterile conditions • Unfiltered sample • On-site analysis preferred 	Dark glass	6 hours/4 °C	Moderate/Low
Carbonate Equilibria pH, HCO ₃ , Ca, Mg	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unfiltered well-sealed sample • On-site analysis (pH, HCO₃) • (Ca/Mg at base laboratory • On acidified sample) 	Any	1 hour (150 days)	Moderate
Oxygen status pE(EH)*, DO, T	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • On site in measuring cell • Avoid aeration • Unfiltered 	Any	0.1 hour	High/Moderate

*Oxidation-Reduction Potential

Organics TOC, VOC, HC, ClHC, etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unfiltered sample • Avoid volatilization • Direct absorption in cartridges preferred 	Dark glass or teflon	1–7 days (Indefinite for cartridges)	High
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1.1.1. Limitations of Qualitative Groundwater Data Monitoring

Water wells and springs are the first points to consider as a data collection source, and the range of properties to be controlled are those listed by Foster and Gomes, 1989, but a reduced list of parameters will be used to be monitored on a long-term period. The results of this kind of monitoring do not usually correspond to the actual condition of water bodies as they are collected at a specific point and time throughout the whole waterbody resource. The pumping rate and pumping period are other effective variables reducing the reliability of collected data that need to be considered in the interpretation of the results.

1.1.2. Early Warning System of Potential Threats to Groundwater

Regarding groundwater quality monitoring, in most cases, the major requirement is to obtain early warnings of possible threats to water resources. To this end, it is necessary to consider the 3D spatial dimensions of the groundwater flow, and the obtained samples have to be considered as the quality of recharge of the aquifer (not the average quality). In addition, the vertical variation in quality is the other factor that needs to be considered.

During the recent developments of urban and industrial waste disposal to groundwater and the intensification of agricultural cultivations, it is necessary to consider the possible threats scenarios in designing the piezometers networks.

2. Groundwater Monitoring Networks and Strategies in Five Case Studies' Countries

2.1. Spain

Institutional Setting and Purpose

The Ministry for Ecological Transition and Demographic Challenge is in charge of groundwater monitoring in Spain. The Ministry executes the Governmental policy on energy and the environment for the transition to a more ecological and social productive model. The objective of the monitoring network was adapted in accordance with the EU Water Framework Directive (WFD) when hundreds of new piezometers were introduced in every basin for determining the chemical status of water bodies.

Characteristics of The Network

Historical groundwater data for Spain are available at <https://sig.mapama.gob.es/redes-seguimiento/index.html?herramienta=Piezometros>, last accessed 12/04/2023 repository. This network includes wells with one or two filters, and artesian wells. Commonly data are measured once a month. In total, there are more than 2,700 piezometers included in the network as given in Figure 1.

Processing and Dissemination

The Monitoring Network Information System from the Ministry of Agriculture and Fisheries, Food and Environment and the Ministry for Ecological Transition offers information about the hydrological monitoring in Spain, including the groundwater monitoring network (Figure 1).

Since 2011, the management of the network has been done by the General Water Authority (DGA). By selecting a well, metadata (coordinates, elevation well depth and others) and time series (all monthly historical data) are visualized in the system. This information can also be downloaded (in PDF or Excel files). Recently, the option of bulk download of the entire database is possible.

Figure 1. Groundwater monitoring network of Spain. Source: (Information System of Monitoring Networks and Hydrological Information from MITECO, Spain)

2.2. Greece

Institutional Setting and Purpose

The Special Secretariat for Water under the Greek Ministry of Environment and Energy is in charge of the National Monitoring Programme of Greece is in charge of hydrological monitoring network. Regarding groundwater, the Institute of Geology and Mineral Exploration (IGME) has been the main promoter of the programme since 2000. The National Monitoring Network has been active since 2012. In addition, each of the 14 prefectures of Greece have their own monitoring programmes through private boreholes.

Characteristics of The Network

The National Monitoring Network operates 1,392 stations dedicated to groundwater quality and quantity in the main groundwater bodies of the country. Stations are divided in two categories: surveillance and operational stations. While surveillance stations monitor water bodies of good status only during a certain period, operational status stations continuously monitor water bodies that failed at achieving good status.

Processing and Dissemination

Data can be found in several sources, such as in the National Data Bank of Hydrological and Meteorological Information (NDBHMI) and in the website and map portal of the National

Water Monitoring Network. One product available in this portal is the boundaries and characterization of groundwater bodies (GWB) per River Basin District, developed in the framework of River Basin Management Plans under the EU WFD, depicting the quantitative and qualitative status of groundwater bodies. Monitoring data can be obtained directly via the website but can also be requested via the Special Secretariat for Water. In addition, data from the 14 prefectures of Greece can be obtained through their water resources directorates. The geoportal of the National Mineral Exploration Research Centre also provides open geospatial data and services for Greece, and data can be obtained from here via request. It is noteworthy that, in general, all official data can be found in the National Geodata Portal as well as given in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Groundwater monitoring stations of Greece source taken from (National Geodata Portal, Greece)

2.3. Portugal

Institutional Setting and Purpose

The Portuguese Environmental Agency (APA) is in charge of the National Groundwater Monitoring Network of Portugal. The monitoring policy of APA includes not only the measurement networks but also measuring instruments, collection and validation procedures, the database system for data storage, and simulation models to support water management and planning.

Characteristics of The Network

The National Water Resources Information System (SNIRH) contains 22,639 groundwater registered points, 7,864 of them have detailed information. At a national level, 592 points belong to the 'quantity network' and 780 to the 'quality network' given in the following repository <https://snirh.apambiente.pt>, last accessed on 12/04/2023 (Figure 3).

Processing and Dissemination

The monitoring stations can be visualized in an interactive portal maintained by the SNIRH, as illustrated in Figure 3. The groundwater quantity report is based on the quantitative groundwater monitoring network and contains an assessment of groundwater level change country-wide. In most aquifer systems, the measurements started in the 1970s, and the frequency of observations is monthly. In the last several years, some piezometers have been equipped with sensors and the data are monitored daily. The groundwater quantity report plays an important role in alerting the decreasing groundwater level, especially during drought periods.

Figure 3. Groundwater Monitoring Network of Portugal. Source (SNIRH)

2.4. Tunisia

Institutional Setting and Purpose

The Tunisian groundwater monitoring network and management are coordinated by the General Directorate of Water Resources (DGRE), with the support of the National Water Distribution Utility (SONEDE). Even though the groundwater monitoring network is relatively dense and active since 1970 (Figure 4), it is not centralised and accessible, limiting its assessment and further recommendation for improvement (increase monitoring frequency and using high frequency and automatized sensors etc).

Characteristics of The Network

Monitoring of groundwater levels is done twice a year by 24 departments of the DGRE. Through a network of more than 2,000 shallow wells and more than 1,100 deep wells the network of Tunisian groundwater monitoring is given in Figure 4.

Processing and Dissemination

DGRE publishes an annual report with the results of the monitoring of the deep aquifers, and every 5 years a report with the results of the monitoring of the shallow aquifers.

Figure 4. Tunisian monitoring network of groundwater levels according to Besbes et al. (2009)

2.5. Turkey

Institutional Setting and Purpose

State Hydraulic Works (Devlet Su İşleri, DSI), founded in 1954, is the state entity responsible for groundwater monitoring throughout Turkey and the sole authorized enforcing entity in groundwater governance. DSI's responsibilities include drilling wells for groundwater monitoring, research and distribution, protection of groundwater, registry of groundwater use, gathering and evaluation of data, and dissemination of irrigated farming and land consolidation. DSI currently operates under the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry. It is organized under 18 regional departments with the general directorate located in the capital Ankara.

The purpose of the groundwater well and surface water monitoring network operated by DSI is to monitor both water quality and quantity and to use that information in water resource management.

Characteristics of The Network

Historical groundwater data in Turkey are available upon request from DSI general directorate. The total number of monitoring wells in Turkey in 2021 was 1,396 monthly monitoring wells and 2,198 seasonal monitoring wells. Besides the piezometric heads, the monitoring data includes the coordinates of the monitoring points, ground surface elevation, the well depth and in some instances soil classification. The country is divided into 25 watersheds as shown in Figure 5, with Konya Closed Basin being basin 16. The number of wells within each basin is given in Table 4.

Figure 5. Twenty-five water basins of Turkey

Table 4. Number of monitoring wells in each basin of Turkey

Basin No	Basin Name	Monitoring Wells (2021)	
		Monthly Monitoring Wells	Seasonal Monitoring Wells
01	Meriç Ergene	39	25
02	Marmara	52	15
03	Susurluk	55	109
04	Kuzey Ege	44	28
05	Gediz	67	85
06	Küçük Menderes	56	92

07	Büyük Menderes	84	37
08	Batı Akdeniz	38	74
09	Antalya	73	73
10	Burdur Göller	13	18
11	Akarçay	44	9
12	Sakarya	212	252
13	Batı Karadeniz	0	31
14	Yeşilirmak	53	201
15	Kızılırmak	184	633
16	Konya Kapalı	255	170
17	Doğu Akdeniz	10	34
18	Seyhan	38	67
19	Asi	23	31
20	Ceyhan	57	12
21	Fırat - Dicle	177	175
22	Doğu Karadeniz	2	0
23	Çoruh	2	4
24	Aras	34	54
25	Van Gölü	0	0
Total		1396	2198

Processing and Dissemination

All water-related data collected from Turkey's groundwater and surface water resources are collected in a central water database (Su very tabanı, SVT) operated by DSI. The purpose of the SVT system is to store, report and utilize the data obtained as a result of the measurement, evaluation and modelling studies of all kinds of water resources used. The SVT system is accessible to DSI authorized employees only. The option of direct public downloading of the database is currently not available. Upon written request and approval by the DSI general directorate, the data are downloaded and shared.

Recently 122 high resolution wells (automatic monitoring with frequency on the order of minutes) have been installed in the Konya Closed Basin. These wells, which were installed in 2019, monitor water level, electrical conductivity and temperature. Transition to high resolution monitoring is underway or being planned for other basins of Turkey.

Table 5. Summary of data availability for each case study country at the national level

Country	Institutional Setting	Number of Piezometers	Frequency of Monitoring	Indicators Used	Database
Spain	The Ministry for Ecological Transition and Demographic Challenge	2,700	Once a month	Coordinates, elevation well depth	General Water Authority (DGA)
Greece	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Institute of Geology and Mineral Exploration (IGME) Each of the 14 prefectures of Greece have their own monitoring programmes 	1,392	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Water bodies of good status only during a certain period Continuously monitor water bodies that failed at achieving good status. 	Boundaries and characterization of groundwater bodies (GWB) per River Basin District	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> National Data Bank of Hydrological and Meteorological Information (NDBHMI) National Water Monitoring Network National Mineral Exploration Research Centre National Geodata Portal
Portugal	The Portuguese Environmental Agency (APA)	592 points for quality monitoring, 780 points for quantity network	Since 1970 it is monitored monthly, Recent year some piezometers are monitored daily	-	National Water Resources Information System (SNIRH)
Tunisia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> General Directorate of Water Resources (DGRE) National Water Distribution Utility (SONEDE) 	2,000 shallow wells and 1,100 deep wells	twice a year	-	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DGRE publishes an annual report for deep aquifers Every 5 years for shallow aquifers.
Turkey	State Hydraulic Works (DSI), under the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry	3,594 (2021)	1,396 monthly monitoring wells and 2,198 seasonally monitoring wells, newly installed high-resolution wells monitor every few minutes	Coordinates, elevation, well depth	State Hydraulic Works upon written request and approval

3. Recommendation Towards Systematic Monitoring and Data Sharing in the MED Region

In-situ data remain an essential component for sustainable groundwater management and protection. For instance, in-situ data are required for models' calibration and validation, reporting obligations for different directives and developing new monitoring alternatives such as Earth Observation (EO). Groundwater monitoring networks and strategies in the five case study countries were generally developed in the 1970s and 1980s when water consumption and environmental problems were completely different from today's concerns. Today emerging environmental problems arising from the increasing effects of climate change have resulted in additional needs for advanced understanding of physical processes using additional parameters at finer spatiotemporal resolution. Thus, continuous monitoring network updates are urgently needed to keep detailed assessment of water resources and environmental status benefiting from advanced technologies and data assimilation capabilities.

In-situ data analysis of case study countries was beneficial to understand the spatiotemporal changes in groundwater over the last decades, particularly in Portugal, Spain and Italy. These countries have centralised and harmonized groundwater level data. Also, they have relatively dense and long-term in-situ data allowing for decadal assessment of groundwater trends. Even though the lack of measurement continuity among the monitoring wells, results helped gain insights into groundwater depletion and its spatiotemporal evolution in time. Detailed groundwater assessment requires information on threshold values of key groundwater indicators such as minimum groundwater level for sustainable exploitation and ecological limit. These boundary conditions are relevant to evaluate the degree of occurrence of deterioration phenomena (such as eutrophication and depletion). Of course, the conclusions of in-situ data analyses are limited as they depend on the data availability and aquifer system characteristics in terms of geology, land use, hydrology etc. This information has the same weight to groundwater level data to ensure enhanced assessment that lead to preventive management. Thus, this information should be shared always with the raw data.

Systematic monitoring in typical and strategic sampling locations could better assess the decadal changes of groundwater status and compared to random monitoring with undefined gauging stations and under varying monitoring frequency and duration. Also, to maximise the

beneficial use of in-situ data results, they should be interpreted simultaneously, with remote sensing data and modelling data. This will open new horizons of information gathering and knowledge coproduction.

In-situ data also should be shared at the right time. The right time means at the appropriate time when management is required or new scientific evidence is needed to fill a knowledge gap. Sharing in-situ data too late can lead to mismanagement and wrong decision-making, resulting in severe and irreversible environmental problems.

3.1. Limitations to Data-Sharing

Overall, considering all case studies countries, there is a reliance on in-situ measurements. This is exacerbated by concerns around data sharing by data owners. As a result, there is a need to find and use complementary alternative data sources such as remote sensing and Earth Observation, modelling and maybe citizen science in the future. In addition, there is a need for improved capacity building, including data analysis, data management, and data sharing policies.

Limitations to data sharing can be explained by the following feedback:

- A “north-south” divide where data is provided to funded projects, with limited benefit to in-country data providers.
- Past experiences where collaborators requested data who then went on to use the data without citing or acknowledging the data sources. There were also concerns that the shared data is being used without permissions, impacting planned publications by the data providers.
- There is a lack of data sharing policies/protocols, with these sometimes being specific to the country or organisation/institution or limited by clauses in donor-funded projects. Thus, a standard protocol for data sharing is needed to ensure data providers retain data ownership and recognition. An example to use is the existing data repository such as IGRAC - International Groundwater Resources Assessment Centre, the which allows data providers to select from different levels of data sharing.

- Development of a common data-management system, with agreed data types and formats that allows for better collaboration between organisations/institutions/countries. This database option should have ownership by the data providers to ensure maintenance and longevity. There is a general lack of internal databases to store data in an easily accessible format, exacerbated when databases are shared between organisations/institutions/countries. Due to a lack of standard formats, there can be data structuring and formatting problems. As a result, there was a consensus that there is need to agree at the start of a project/initiative on a common data-management system, with agreed data types and formats that allows for better collaboration between organisations/institutions/countries. In some countries, it was noted that there is a need for enhanced data sharing via a central validated repository; however, it was noted that this is currently not incentivised, and that this would need long-term funding to collect, maintain and make data available to the database.
- While databases were developed with useful data, these were noted to be specific to a project with maintenance stopping after the project ended; thereby resulting in a loss of access to data by stakeholders.
- There was a call for in-country capacity building in the beneficial aspects of data sharing, responsible use of data and implementing advanced monitoring technology such as EO and optical sensors, as well as data storage, processing and analysis.

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